

St. Dominic College of Asia through the years: A trend analysis of the organizational diagnosis in the years 2011-2018

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Abstract

This study analyzes the Organizational Diagnosis Survey results from 2011 to 2018 on the following areas: purpose, structure, leadership, relationship, rewards, helpful mechanism, and attitude towards change. Using a validated and reliability tested tool ($\alpha=.81$), employees of St. Dominic College of Asia were asked to answer the questionnaire according to whether they are very satisfied, satisfied, slightly satisfied, neutral, slightly unsatisfied, unsatisfied, and strongly unsatisfied. The results show that in almost all areas with the exception of rewards ($x=2.69$), the employees are satisfied considering the indicators demonstrated. Moreover, the ratings slightly had a slump in the year 2015-2016, but it regains momentum from 2016 to 2018 as the ratings went slightly higher. Thus, it is recommended for this institution to revisit its rewards system through salaries and benefits and find ways to improve its strategies.

Keywords: Organizational culture; organizational diagnosis; trend analysis; open systems.

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To cite this article:

Aban, M. R. N. (2023). St. Dominic College of Asia through the years: A trend analysis of the organizational diagnosis in the years 2011-2018. *SDCA Asia-Pacific Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 5(1), 60-63.

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8031392

Introduction

A cutting-edge method for understanding an organization across all levels, from what is most visible to the most hidden areas, is organizational diagnosis. Different diagnostic approaches can be applied in various situations depending on the preferences, requirements, and priorities of our clients. In order to identify the underlying causes of an organization's problems and offer advice on how to strengthen them, human resources or organizational development and transformation practitioners who work within in an organization or have been working as paid consultants would use these models (McFillen et al., 2013 as cited in Furgoch, 2016). In any event, the diagnostic models provide a blueprint or tool for separating the organization into its component elements in order to describe it in greater detail and to better visualize how each part interacts with the others. From the diagnostic itself, it is also feasible to start identifying issues that exist within an organization (Furgoch, 2016).

Both open systems and closed systems may contain diagnostic models. All organizational components are interconnected, as shown by open system models, and a change in a single aspect would most likely have an effect on the others. Open systems imitate Lewin's field theory, which states that "the totality of coexisting facts which are conceived as mutually interdependent" (Lewin, 1951) and Myrdal's principle of cumulative effect, which states that "a change in one brings about a change in the other, which in turn brings on more change." In what is essentially a constant state of transition, the changes may be subtle enough to appear stable.

However, most structures contain several interrelated components, making them much more complicated (Hickman, 2009). In addition, open systems models take the enterprise's external environment into consideration while making choices and carrying out improvements. Thus, an organization's external environment can affect an organization's inputs, internal operations (e.g., strategies, human resource structures, procedures) and organizational outputs (e.g., products, advertisements). This promotes that the interaction of roles, personalities, leadership, transitions, and decision making is extremely complex for organizations.

The open system concept embraces the idea of being more powerful and effective than every part taken separately, despite the fact that this complexity is nearly too impossible to deal with all at once. The open systems framework is remarkable in that it provides constant feedback throughout the process. With that, the human resource staff shall have inputs (e.g., knowledge and human capital), transformations (e.g., social and technological components), and outputs (e.g., goods, services, and intellectual capital). There is continuous input in each of these categories that helps to move forward the company or rethink concepts and thoughts among others that did not succeed and had to be changed. This is similar to the principle of fostering trial and error which aims to attempt a lot of things and retain what works. To ensure effective and timely input, communication becomes an essential component in this model.

The open systems model is a preferred model despite the evolving and changing environment over the last decade. To better evaluate and support an organization that is constantly changing and requires flexibility to adjust to the environment and changing demands of customers, we must be able to apply diagnostic techniques which encourage this flexibility and adaptability.

This form of flexibility and adaptability is not advocated by the closed system model since it simply fully ignores the external world and focuses too much on the internal components. Neglecting outside influences suggests a weak organization that will be unable to handle change when it occurs, which makes them vulnerable to catastrophe or collapse. In addition, closed systems models promote one correct way of doing things. This prevents the development of the business and its employees because it does not foster any learning within the organization, which is essential in today's society.

An organizational diagnostic model is another type of diagnostic paradigm that examines a company from an outside or a high-level perspective. At a more comprehensive level that focuses on group level diagnosis and person level diagnosis, similar models may be followed. The organizational level diagnostic adheres to the open systems paradigm, which assumes that all components are interconnected and that the environment, particularly in inputs, has a crucial role in the organization.

Culture is a crucial factor in the intervention process because, as research indicates, it is important to consider effective culture for change efforts to be successful and there will eventually need to be a cultural change involved in the company. Studies show that *"the most frequently cited reason given for failure was a neglect of the organization's culture...many efforts to improve organizational performance fail because the fundamental culture of the organization – values, ways of thinking, managerial styles, paradigms, approaches to problem-solving – remain the same"* (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). Therefore, companies would undoubtedly need to undergo cultural changes in order for any changes to enhance organizational success.

Organizational diagnoses may usually be made when leadership has established problems they want to correct. People desire to try to boost themselves more when things are working well within an organization. In either situation there exist two *"major sets of problems that all groups, no matter what their size, must deal with: (1) Survival, growth, and adaptation in their environment; and (2) Internal integration that permits daily functioning and the ability to adapt and learn"* (Schein & Schein, 2017).

Organizational Growth and Development

Organizational growth requires adaptation and adaptive leadership. The characteristics of effective changes include an awareness of urgency, the development of a powerful team of change agents, the execution of an objective and plan through intentional and carefully designed planning, the dissemination of the vision for change to the organization, the responsibility of team members to support and participate in efforts of change, the production of short-term wins, and the celebration of success and the production of more change, as well as anchoring cultural shifts to prevent returning to the status quo (Kotter, 2012).

Those starting transformation projects are setting oneself up for failure by overlooking or failing to identify the organization's essence. There are numerous ways to learn about and comprehend corporate culture, but none of them compared to going there and seeing it for yourself. Furthermore, choosing the ideal people to speak with and preparing smart questions to ask will help you gather reliable and high-quality information. Finally, the organization needs to be mindful that different employees might not share the same perspective on culture. Therefore, it is crucial that professionals consider gathering information from many sources and making diagnoses and interventions. If the culture is examined, it may be probable that some of the problems are being caused by a value misalignment.

Furgoch (2016) argued that there are several factors that contribute to the capacity of an organization to navigate effectively through a situation of change or turnaround and be able to maintain it. Organizations need to begin transforming in order for a cultural revolution to take place, starting with creating a sense of urgency within their staff (Asuch-Duodu et al., 2019). Culture must be considered when teams step forward in the process of transition. If culture is not considered throughout the diagnostic process, it is likely that the measures for improvement or change will fail.

Organizational changes inside the HR department can also greatly aid the transformation process without adopting a large-scale change strategy. These can be viewed as modest adjustments to the organization's policies, programs, procedures, technology, human resource management systems, and strategies, among others, but they can have a big impact on how well it does. The concept behind interventions is that they are little, relatively straightforward, and reasonably priced as compared to extensive, long-term adaptations. Organizations may not be willing to make big adjustments, nor do they constantly have the time or resources to do so. The use of interventions can help to define objectives, plans, and ambitions, produce short-term successes that advance these objectives, and test upcoming efforts before committing a whole country or continent to change in a single division or region. The efficacy of interventions on this level may be shown by repeated consulting engagements that improved organizational performance and enhanced leadership and team member support for additional measures or larger-scale change efforts (Furgoch, 2016).

Through this, we can figure out the components of an organization's human resources by using organizational diagnosis. From there, we may assess how well those HR processes align with the organization's culture, strategy, and goals. When people come across items that do not work in the human resource structures, the human resource recommends interventions that will provide organizational alignment and offer additional value to workers in both tangible and intangible rewards. Included in the tangible rewards are equal payment schemes, compensation systems, daily reviews, enhanced performance evaluation systems, training availability (technical, leadership, cultural, and diversity) and career growth opportunities. Financial support for coaching and mentorship, corporate pride, and flexible work schedules to accommodate family and health requirements and reduce stress are examples of intangible benefits.

St. Dominic College of Asia: Response to Challenges

St. Dominic College of Asia has been in the business of providing quality education for more than 15 years and with that span of time, it has been experiencing several milestones which people could not imagine from a “baby” like this institution. Physically, SDCA has three buildings erected on a once swamp nearby salt-producing field. From a caregiving training course, SDCA is now a proud academic institution offering 17 academic programs. Attuned to the vision and mission of its founders, SDCA is now an academic institution that has undergone various accreditations from Philippine Association on Colleges and Universities Commission on Accreditation (PACUCOA) and International Organization for Standardization (ISO), thus, it is expected that the quality of education it is now offering is at par with the leading higher education institutions of Metro Manila.

With success, come challenges. One of these challenges is SDCA’s integrity of its internal recesses, its culture, its people, its processes, and its system. This organizational diagnosis questionnaire (ODQ) was created with the intention of providing survey-feedback data for thorough diagnostic efforts. It is, therefore, the aim of this research to determine how SDCA responded to these internal challenges by analyzing the results of the organizational diagnosis from 2011-2018, as conducted by the HR office in cooperation with the Research Development Office. Further, this seeks to assess the improvements in its internal structure and system throughout the seven (7) years using trend analysis, as perceived by the organization’s employees.

Methodology

This study utilized the descriptive, trend analysis design of research in which data from 2011 to 2018 are evaluated and investigated for possible points of discussion and further research. To gather the data from all employees of SDCA, a tool, Organizational Diagnosis Questionnaire as adapted by Robert C. Preziosi (1980) was used, in which are classified into Purpose, Structure, Leadership, Relationship, Rewards, Helpful Mechanism, and Attitude Towards Change. The scale is from 1 to 7 with 1 as very satisfied and 7 as strongly unsatisfied. This instrument is a survey-feedback tool made to gather information about how an organization works (Kaur & Sharma, 2015). To identify the fields of operation that could benefit from an organization's management effort, it measures the views of people inside an organization or work unit. The model and instrument both demonstrate an approach for examining connections between various factors that have an impact on how a company is managed. The informal components of the system are measured by the ODQ. The consultant or facilitator may also need to gather data on the formal parts and look at any gaps between them.

Results and Discussion

The data shows that employees of SDCA are “Satisfied” in almost all areas except rewards, in which employees evaluated to be slightly satisfied (x=2.69). Of all areas, the highest rating goes with leadership (x=2.04). This is followed closely by purpose (x=2.05), relationship (x=2.08), attitude towards change (x=2.21), helpful mechanism (x=2.23), and structure (x=2.33).

This suggests that SDCA should improve more in its rewards system so as to improve the future ratings in this area. Although “Satisfied” is acceptable, there are still plenty of rooms for improvement as SDCA’s goal should be higher than this which is very satisfied. The summary of the organizational diagnosis survey is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Summary of results of organization diagnosis survey from 2011-2018

Areas	2011-2012	2012-2013	2013-2014	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	Average	QI
Purpose	2.08	2.05	2.08	2.01	2.43	1.97	1.73	2.05	S
Structure	2.45	2.10	2.31	2.32	2.90	2.18	2.05	2.33	S
Leadership	2.15	2.04	2.03	1.89	2.49	1.94	1.74	2.04	S
Relationship	2.28	2.07	2.09	1.91	2.43	1.99	1.79	2.08	S
Rewards	2.92	2.25	2.95	2.66	3.20	2.41	2.46	2.69	SS
Helpful Mechanism	2.56	2.10	2.25	2.15	2.66	2.09	1.81	2.23	S
Attitude towards Change	2.40	2.09	2.23	2.25	2.55	2.05	1.93	2.21	S

Legend: 1.00-1.59: Very satisfied (VS); 1.60-2.59: Satisfied (S); 2.60-3.59: Slightly satisfied (SS); 3.60-4.59: Neutral (N); 4.60-5.59: Slightly Unsatisfied (SU); 5.60-6.59: Unsatisfied (U); 6.60-7.00: Strongly unsatisfied (StU)

Note: 1 is the highest and 7 is the lowest rate.

As to how each year has been rated from 2011 to the present, Figure 1 shows below the summary graph of the organizational diagnosis survey. It can be gleaned from the graph in Figure 1 that from 2011 to 2018, there is no significant change in the trend except in 2015-2016 in which the ratings slightly plunged but it recovered in AY 2016-2017 to 2017-2018. Moreover, the graph also demonstrates that the area of rewards slightly veers away from the rest of the field, as shown in Table 1, in which in this area, employees are just slightly satisfied.

Figure 1. Summary graph of the organizational diagnosis survey

Going into the specifics, when it comes to purpose, it is clear that the employees of SDCA know and are satisfied with the purpose of the institution as there is no significant curve that shows significant deviation from the rest of the areas, same with structure, leadership, relationship, helpful mechanism, attitude towards change. Oriented with the institution's vision and mission, the employee's ratings in purpose signifies that it upholds and affirms what SDCA has been asserting for on the trifocal areas of instruction, research, and community outreach. Although, they need to further acculturate themselves with what SDCA has been espousing for, as shown by the ratings which can still go up to the point of "very satisfied."

When it comes to leadership, the community is basically cognizant of how leaders of the institution worked and exemplified servant leadership; most specifically the president who is very much hands-on with the job as the captain of the ship steering SDCA to fulfilling its vision and mission. However, this can still go higher same with the relationship, helpful mechanism, attitude towards change, and most importantly rewards. This is similar with the study of Wang et al. (2017), suggesting that intra-organizational changes within the institution may improve inter-organizational relationships between the school and the community themselves.

Conclusions and Recommendations

From the data gathered and analyzed, this study yielded some conclusions, to wit:

1. The employees of SDCA are generally "Satisfied" with the purpose, leadership, structure, relationship, helpful mechanism, and attitude towards change. However, they are "Slightly satisfied" with SDCA's rewards system. Thus, it is recommended that SDCA should improve further its strategies to enhance further its rewards system as expressed through the salary and benefits of the employees. This is to improve its ratings in this area in the future.
2. There is a big room for improvement in all areas from just "Satisfied" to "Very satisfied" in all areas surveyed. Thus, it is recommended for SDCA to evaluate its purpose, structure, leadership, relationship, rewards, helpful mechanism, and attitude towards change by conducting further study to explore the reasons of this "not too high" rating despite SDCA's efforts to make these areas well-addressed. Moreover, a qualitative study can be done to verify and expound on the reasons for the employees' answers to the organizational diagnosis survey. It is also recommended that the human resources office conduct focus group discussion among its employees to determine the ways and means to improve those areas mentioned.

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